

On the Polarographic Reduction of 2-Aminobenzothiazoles

WAHID U. MALIK* and RAJEEV JAIN**

Chemistry Department, University of Roorkee, Roorkee-247 672

2-AMINOBENZOTHIAZOLES are widely used as precursors for the synthesis of compounds of medicinal importance¹⁻⁴. Unlike other heterocycles they do not undergo reduction at the d.m.e., despite their having a reducible C=NH bond. Their polarographic reduction even at higher potential is not achieved by extending the potential range with lithium chloride and tetramethyl ammonium bromide as supporting electrolytes^{5,6}. Although it is difficult to explain the highly polarographically inert nature of these thiazoles, it can perhaps be attributed to the high aromaticity developed in them by the phenyl group.

These compounds undergo complex ion formation with transition metals⁷ in the pH range 2.0 to 6.0. In the higher pH range no such reaction takes place and simply the metal hydrous oxides are precipitated. However, when the metal salt solution was added to the thiazole solution in NH₄Cl-NH₄OH buffer (pH 9.3) the resulting mixture remained unchanged and could be subjected to polarographic analysis. Subsequently, these thiazoles were investigated polarographically using base medium, corresponding to Brdicka solution 0.01M COCl₂, 0.1M NH₄Cl and 0.1M NH₄OH.

Realising that no apparent similarity existed in the role of Brdicka solution in the proteins and in our aminobenzothiazoles, the COCl₂ in the base electrolyte was replaced with other Lewis acids, e.g., nickel, manganese, zinc and aluminium halides. It was found to our much satisfaction that well defined reduction waves, just similar to that in the presence of cobalt chloride, were obtained here.

It may be argued that the above mentioned polarographic waves may be due to the reduction of the metal thiazole complexes, since no possible evidence of complex ion formation on the basis of spectrophotometric and electrometric techniques was forthcoming, and the half wave potentials of metals and their complexes with ammonia are quite different from the E_{1/2} of Brdicka solution⁸. Interestingly enough, the E_{1/2} of 2-aminobenzothiazoles in Co²⁺ and Ni²⁺ ammonical solutions are more positive than those of the metal and the corresponding metal amine complex (Table 1). Furthermore, shift in half-wave potential of 2-ABT with various substituents and a good correlation between E_{1/2} and σ (Fig. 1) strongly support the view that 2-aminobenzothiazoles alone were undergoing reduction at d.m.e.

Metal ion	-E _{1/2} , V	Metal ion +2-ABT	-E _{1/2} , V	Metal amines	-E _{1/2} , V
Co ²⁺ aq.	1.29	Co ²⁺ aq. +2-ABT	1.12	Co(NH ₃) ₆ H ₂ O	1.40
Ni ²⁺ aq.	1.10	Ni ²⁺ aq. +2-ABT	0.88	Ni(NH ₃) ₆ ²⁺	1.09
Mn ²⁺ aq.	1.48	Mn ²⁺ aq. +2-ABT	1.60	Mn(NH ₃) ₆ ²⁺	1.65
Zn ²⁺ aq.	0.99	Zn ²⁺ aq. +2-ABT	1.22	Zn(NH ₃) ₆ ²⁺	1.33

Fig. 1. Plot of $-E_{1/2}$ vs σ for 2-aminobenzothiazoles in cobalt chloride.

Incidentally, these studies can provide a new approach to the reduction of difficultly reducible compounds.

Experimental

2-Aminobenzothiazoles having substituents in the benzene ring viz., H, 4-Cl, 5-Cl, 6-Cl, 4-CH₃, 5-CH₃, 6-CH₃, 4-OCH₃, 5-OCH₃, 6-OCH₃, 4-OC₂H₅, 6-OC₂H₅, 4-Br, 4,6-(CH₃)₂, 4,5-(CH₃)₂ and 5,6-(CH₃)₂ were synthesized by the method reported earlier⁹. The purity of the compounds was ascertained by repeated recrystallisation and tlc. Stock solutions (1.10 × 10⁻³M) of the compounds were prepared in methanol (AnalaR). 0.01M solutions of cobalt chloride, nickel chloride, zinc chloride, manganese chloride and aluminium chloride were pre-

* Present address : Vice-Chancellor, Kashmir University, Hazratbal, Srinagar-190 006 (J & K).

** Present address : Chemistry Department, Jiwaji University, Gwalior-474 011.

pared in doubly distilled water. The solutions used in these studies for recording the polarograms of the thiazoles were of the composition 0.1M NH₄Cl, 0.1M NH₃ and 0.001 M metal chlorides.

Apparatus and procedure : The polarographic curves were recorded on the Cambridge pen recording polarograph. The capillary characteristic was 1.27 mg 2/3 S- $\frac{1}{2}$ in 1.0M KCl. A saturated calomel electrode was used as the reference electrode and the temperature was maintained at 30.0 $\pm$ 0.1°. Inert atmosphere in the cell was kept by passing purified nitrogen gas for 10 min. pH measurements were made on the ELICO LI-10 pH meter.

Metal chlorides (1.0 ml), liq. NH₃ (1.0 ml), NH₄Cl (1.0 ml), water (6.0 ml) and 1.0 ml of the compound were mixed thoroughly with a stream of nitrogen. No maxima suppressor was used in the case of cobalt and nickel salts but the addition of 0.5 ml of 0.1% gelatin was found necessary in the case of manganese and zinc salts. For determining the value of 'n', the number of electrons involved in the reduction, the method of Devries and Kroon¹⁰ was used using a mercury pool cathode. The temperature coefficient was determined by Nejedly's¹¹ method.

Results and Discussion

The polarograms of these compounds were recorded in various buffers in the pH range 2.0-12.0. No reduction wave was obtained. In the Brdicka solution a single well defined reduction wave was obtained (Fig. 2). Similar waves were obtained when cobalt was replaced by other metal ions, viz., nickel, manganese, zinc and aluminium. Precipitation of the hydrous oxide took place with chromium and titanium salts and polarograms with these metal ions in ammonium chloride ammonia medium were not realized.

[Curves (1) and (2) start at -0.9V, (3) starts at -0.8V, (4) and (5) starts at -0.6V and (6) starts at -1.16V]

Fig. 2. Some typical polarograms of 2-aminobenzothiazoles at concentration $1 \times 10^{-4}M$.

- (1) R = H in CoCl₂; (2) R = 6-CH₃ in CoCl₂;
(3) R = 4-Cl in CoCl₂; (4) R = H in NiCl₂;
(5) R = 5-Cl in NiCl₂; (6) R = H in ZnCl₂.

The polarographic behaviour of these compounds was entirely different from the usually reported behaviour in Brdicka solution in which a catalytic¹² wave is invariably obtained. On the other hand,

the waves were found to be diffusion controlled. The irreversible nature of the waves was confirmed from log plots as well as from the shift in E_{1/2} to more negative potential with the increase ($1.0 \times 10^{-4}M$ to $2.5 \times 10^{-4}M$) in concentration of the depolarizer¹³. The value of 'n', the number of electrons involved in the reduction at the d.m.e., was found to be two.

TABLE 2—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF 2-AMINO-BENZOTHAZOLES IN BRDICKA SOLUTION

No.	R	-E _{1/2} , V	ΔE _{1/2} , V	$\frac{i_d}{\mu A}$	αn	σ
1.	H	1.12	—	4.95	0.48	0.00
2.	4-CH ₃	1.14	0.02	5.00	0.42	-0.17
3.	5-CH ₃	1.16	0.04	0.95	0.50	-0.07
4.	6-CH ₃	1.20	0.08	5.12	0.50	-0.17
5.	4-Cl	1.08	0.04	5.25	0.48	+0.20
6.	5-Cl	1.06	0.06	5.00	0.42	+0.37
7.	6-Cl	1.04	0.08	5.10	0.42	+0.23
8.	4-OCH ₃	1.26	0.14	4.95	0.50	-0.39
9.	5-OCH ₃	1.18	0.06	5.10	0.48	-0.11
10.	6-OCH ₃	1.18	0.06	5.25	0.48	-0.27
11.	4-OC ₂ H ₅	1.24	0.12	5.00	0.42	-0.35
12.	6-OC ₂ H ₅	1.22	0.10	5.20	0.42	-0.25
13.	4-Br	1.06	0.06	5.25	0.30	+0.21
14.	4,6-(CH ₃) ₂	1.22	0.10	5.20	0.48	-0.34
15.	4,5-(CH ₃) ₂	1.18	0.06	5.00	0.42	-0.24
16.	5,6-(CH ₃) ₂	1.24	0.12	5.00	0.42	-0.24

The half-wave potential of 2-aminobenzothiazoles in the presence of different metal ions in ammonium chloride ammonia solution are given in Table 3.

TABLE 3—HALF-WAVE POTENTIALS OF 2-ABT IN DIFFERENT METAL IONS

No.	R	-E _{1/2} , V			
		Co	Ni	Mn	Zn
1.	H	1.12	0.88	1.60	1.22
2.	4-CH ₃	1.14	0.90	1.68	1.27
3.	5-CH ₃	1.16	0.93	1.68	1.30
4.	6-CH ₃	1.20	0.98	1.74	1.30
5.	4-Cl	1.08	0.98	1.80	1.26
6.	5-Cl	1.06	0.96	1.70	1.24
7.	6-Cl	1.04	0.94	1.68	1.25
8.	4-OCH ₃	1.26	0.98	1.56	1.28
9.	5-OCH ₃	1.18	0.96	1.54	1.24
10.	4-OC ₂ H ₅	1.24	0.98	1.62	1.22
11.	6-OC ₂ H ₅	1.22	0.96	1.60	1.20
12.	4-Br	1.06	0.94	1.76	1.20
13.	4,6-(CH ₃) ₂	1.22	0.98	1.78	1.30
14.	4,5-(CH ₃) ₂	1.18	0.94	1.72	1.32
15.	5,6-(CH ₃) ₂	1.24	1.00	1.75	1.36

The 2-aminobenzothiazoles can exist in two tautomeric forms. Of these, the form having the -C=NH is polarographically active.

The reduction of these compounds, can, therefore, be represented as :

COCl₂ being Lewis acid accepts a pair of electrons from the media viz., NH₄OH + NH₄Cl

which in turn attack the $-G=N-$ of 2-aminobenzothiazole (I) to form a donor acceptor complex (II) which is adsorbed at the mercury surface and orient itself on the surface in such a manner that a easily reducible moiety (III) is obtained.

The above view point was further confirmed by replacing cobalt chloride by other metal chlorides viz., nickel chloride, zinc chloride and manganese chloride which can act as a Lewis acid. In all these cases a similar 2e wave was observed (Table 3). An interesting point worth mentioning here was the different Lewis acid character of various metal ions. From Table 3 it is clear that order of capability of accepting a lone pair for various metal ions follows the order :

Effect of substituents : For studying the effect of substituents quantitatively, a sufficient number of derivatives were selected so as to cover a wide range of polar, steric and mesomeric effects of substituents. Since the values of the transfer coefficient and the mechanism of reduction for all the substituted aminobenzothiazoles were similar ($\alpha_n = 0.42$ to 0.50 ; Table 2) the conditions for comparison of substituents quantitatively are fulfilled^{14,15}.

The values of half-wave potentials were correlated with Hammett total substituent constant (σ_x)¹⁶. The plots showing dependence of $E_{1/2}$ on σ are given in Fig. 1. In all these cases not only the substituent *m*- and *p*- but the *ortho* derivatives showed a good correlation. In other reported series of compounds¹⁵, *ortho* derivatives deviate from the $E_{1/2}$ vs σ plots due to steric hindrance. But in these compounds substituents are far away from the reduction site. Therefore, *ortho* derivatives could not sterically hinder the reduction of 2-aminobenzothiazoles. The value of specific reaction constant, ρ , was found to be 0.17 V, which is in good agreement with the value reported in the literature^{17,18}. The positive value of ρ indicated a nucleophilic mechanism. In other words, the reduction of these compounds at d.m.e. involves electron uptake as the potential determining step.

Role of Lewis acids in the reduction of 2-aminobenzothiazoles : As these compounds undergo reduction only in the presence of Lewis acids, the role of Lewis acid in these electrode processes was elucidated. It appeared that a donor acceptor

complex between 2-aminobenzothiazole (2-ABT) and metal plays a determinant role in the reduction of 2-aminobenzothiazoles at d.m.e. This complex is adsorbed through diffusion at the mercury surface (and not simply by adsorption as evinced by the non-existence of adsorption prewave) and orient itself in such a manner that the hydrocarbon part of the 2-ABT points towards the mercury surface and the metal remains far away from the surface. This may be the possible reason for the non-appearance of the reduction wave of metals.

Although it is difficult to assign any definite reason for the non-reducibility of 2-ABT in supporting electrolytes other than the Brdicka solution, the possible explanation can be thought out in terms of inner sphere mechanism. Further evidence of inner sphere mechanism for the reduction of these compounds was obtained by carrying out studies in the presence of a surfactant. Since the electrode surface is negatively charged (E_{max} , 0.62 V), the cationic soap, cetyltrimethylammonium bromide was used. The donor-acceptor complex

would have to compete with the surfactant for the site on the electrode surface, thereby increasing the energy of activation for the formation of the

transition state (---C---NH₂). This will result in a lower rate of reduction.

Rate of reduction (K_{app}) for both inner and outer sphere reduction at the mercury electrode surface is given by the equation^{19,20} :

$$\log K_{app} = \log \frac{i}{FC_b}$$

where *i* is the current density at various applied potentials and C_b is concentration of the depolarizer.

The rate of reduction for 2-ABT in the absence and presence of surfactant is given in Table 4. The plots of $\log K_{app}$ vs potentials *E* was linear for a particular solution of constant concentration of the depolarizer. The values of α_{app} can be evaluated from the slope of plots of $\log K_{app}$ against $-E$ which gives.

$$\alpha_{app} = -\frac{2.303RT}{F} \left(\frac{\log K_{app}}{\delta E} \right)$$

It is clear from Table 4 that the values of α_{app} are quite below 0.5 and K_{app} decreases in presence of surfactant. A very elegant proof of the reduction mechanism based on inner sphere path is thus forthcoming on the basis of polarographic analysis in the presence of surfactants.

TABLE 4—KINETIC DATA FOR ELECTRO REDUCTION IN BRDICKA SOLUTION

R	$-\log K_{app}$ (cms ⁻¹)*		$\Delta \log K_{app}$ b-a	α_{app}		$\left[\frac{\log K_{app}}{\log K_{app}, H} \right]$	ψ
	a	b		a	b		
H	0.266	0.289	0.023	0.019	0.016	1.00	0.96
4-CH ₃	0.260	0.285	0.025	0.020	0.018	1.00	0.90
5-CH ₃	0.260	0.289	0.029	0.019	0.96	1.26	0.96
6-CH ₃	0.250	0.275	0.025	0.018	0.014	1.08	0.92
4-Cl	0.240	0.264	0.025	0.018	0.014	1.08	0.92
5-Cl	0.265	0.285	0.020	0.019	0.015	0.90	0.90
6-Cl	0.252	0.276	0.024	0.018	0.015	1.04	0.90
4-OCH ₃	0.265	0.289	0.024	0.018	0.014	1.04	0.90
5-OCH ₃	0.250	0.276	0.026	0.020	0.017	1.13	0.90
6-OCH ₃	0.240	0.264	0.024	0.018	0.013	1.04	0.96
4-OC ₂ H ₅	0.269	0.285	0.016	0.018	0.014	1.04	0.92
6-OC ₂ H ₅	0.248	0.272	0.024	0.018	0.014	0.80	0.96
4-Br	0.245	0.264	0.019	0.018	0.013	1.04	0.92
4,6-(CH ₃) ₂	0.248	0.272	0.024	0.019	0.015	1.04	0.96
4,5-(CH ₃) ₂	0.258	0.285	0.027	0.018	0.014	1.17	0.96
5,6-(CH ₃) ₂	0.260	0.285	0.025	0.019	0.016	1.08	0.92

* a—in absence of surfactant, b—in presence of surfactant.

References

- R. C. CLINTON, U. J. SALVADOR, S. C. LASKOWSKI and C. M. SUTTER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 950.
- L. S. MIKESKA, *U.S. Patent*, 2,305,278; *Chem. Abs.*, 1952, 46, 10650.
- P. C. EISMANS, E. A. KONOPKA and R. L. MAYER, *Amer. Rev. Tuber.*, 1954, 70, 121.
- K. SINDOLAR, A. DLABOC, J. METYSOVA and B. KAKOE, *Collect. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1975, 40, 1940.
- F. V. STURN and W. HANS, *Angew. Chem.*, 1955, 67, 743.
- J. TIROUFLET, E. LAVIRON, J. METZZER and J. BIOCHARD, *Collect. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1960, 25, 3277.
- W. U. MALIK, P. K. SRIVASTAVA and S. C. MEHRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 46, 486.
- J. HEYROVSKY and J. KUTA, "Principles of Polarography", Academic Press, N.Y., 1966.
- A. HUGERSHOFF, *Ber.*, 1901, 34, 3130.
- T. DEVRIES and J. L. KROON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 2484.
- V. NEJEDLY, *Collect. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1922, 1, 319.
- I. M. KOLTHOFF and J. J. LINGANE, "Polarography", Interscience, N. Y., 2nd Ed., 1956, Vol. 2.
- L. MEITES, "Polarographic Technique", Interscience, N.Y., 1967.
- L. P. HAMMETT, "Physical Organic Chemistry", McGraw Hill, N. Y., 1966.
- P. ZUMMAN, "Substituent Effects in Organic Polarography", Plenum Press, N.Y., 1967.
- H. H. JAFFE, *Chem. Rev.*, 1953, 191.
- B. FLECT and P. ZUMAN, *Collect. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1966, 32, 3066.
- YU. P. KITAEV, G. K. BUDMIKOV and A. E. ARBUZOV, *Izv. Akad. Nauk SSSR. Otd. Khim. Nauk*, 1961, 1772.
- M. J. WEAVER and F. C. ANSON, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1975, 58, 81.
- M. J. WEAVER and F. C. ANSON, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1975, 65, 711.